

www.arseam.com

EXTENT OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG PRIVATE AND GOVERNMENT HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

Benkat Krishna Bharti,

Department of Psychology
Patna University, Patna, India

Abstract

The present inquiry was aimed at studying the organizational commitment among private and government high school teachers with reference to Darbhanga district – a historically well-known town of Mithila region of North Bihar. Total sample consisted of 120 teachers comprising private high school (n=60) and government school (n=60). They were selected randomly from different private and government schools situated at in and around Darbhanga district. The data were collected through questionnaire schedule and the obtained data were analyzed by t test and the value of t was found significant at .01 level of confidence, although both the group of private school and government school teachers have shown favorable inclination towards organizational commitment. The results also revealed that private school teachers group comparatively has higher degree of organizational commitment than government school teachers. The results have been discussed in detail by highlighting the probable reasons for obtaining such a discrepancy of results between the group of private school and government school teachers.

Key Words: Organizational Commitment, Teachers and Schools

INTRODUCTION

It is undoubtedly fact that today's society has become more powerful by utilizing human potentialities and skills at work. This is the effect of the principles of Human

Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers

Resource Utilization strategies. On the basis of this principle our Indian society has also become highly commercialized and modernized based on hi-tech for competing over the global educational market. These days we can observe that our Educational Learning Center's infrastructure has fully well-equipped and as a result of which teachers and students, both are curious to fight at globe by utilizing his/her talents/skills and human resource potentialities to achieve their desired goals by the means of modern education. So, the present study is aimed at studying the extent of organizational commitment among private school and government school teachers with special reference to Darbhanga district- a well-known city of North Bihar, India. It is important to be mentioned here that in recent years, management of personal and life depends on the life orientation of an individual. Although a number of concepts have been introduced, there still exists, a gap to explain wide variety of behaviors in diverse groups. So, it is asserted that organizational commitment is the important variable to be studied among private school teachers and government school teachers with reference to Darbhanga – a well-known district of North Bihar where near about more than one hundred private and government schools are engaged in imparting education without any discrimination of caste, creed, and religion and consequently more than thousands of teachers are affiliated with teaching professions.

The term organizational commitment which has a wide variety of definitions, hence, Organizational Commitment most often defined as (i) strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization (ii) a willingness to exert high levels of effort on behalf of the organization, (iii) a definite belief in and acceptance of, the values and the goals of the organization (Mowday, Porter and Steers, 1982). In fact, organizational commitment is an attitude about individual's faithful to one's friends and to their organization as well which is an ongoing process through which the members of the group expresses their concern for its organizational goals to get succeeded.

Suki and Suki (2011) conducted a study to find out the influence of gender on employee's perception of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Findings revealed that employee's gender has no significant effect on his/her perception of job satisfaction. Further they found that men and women employees have the same level of organizational commitment. Kumari and Jafri (2011) conducted a study to measure the

level of overall organizational commitment of male and female secondary school teachers in Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh. Data was analyzed by applying Mean, SD and t-test. Results showed that overall percentage of female school teachers experienced higher level of organizational commitment as compared to the male teachers. Similar results were found by Zilli and Zahoor (2012) among male and female among higher education teachers. Nagar (2012) conducted a study to evaluate "organizational commitment and job satisfaction among teachers during times of Burnout for developing and tests a model for Burnout and its influence on job satisfaction and organizational commitment". Results showed that with the consideration of job satisfaction & organizational commitment, the mean score of female teachers was found to be higher than male teachers. He concluded that greater job satisfaction among teachers also leads to the increased level of organizational commitment. Misra, Ansari and Khan (2009) conducted the study to measure the organizational commitment among Government and private school teachers. They reported that the private school teachers showed higher organizational commitment as compared to the government school teachers. Gupta and Gehlawat (2013) conducted the study to assess the influence of job satisfaction, work motivation and type of schools on organizational commitment among the sample of 480 secondary school teachers in Rohtak Division of Haryana. The investigators applied Means, SD's and t-test for analyzing the collected data. Findings of the study reported significant effect of type of schools and job satisfaction on the organizational commitment of the teachers. Private school teachers significantly differ with Government school teachers and they possessed higher level of organizational commitment as compared to the Government school teachers. Further, there was no significant difference was found in organizational commitment of private school teachers with high and low level of work motivation and the government school teachers with high level of work motivation were reported to be better than their counterparts with respect to their organizational commitment.

[Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers](#)

In addition to these, commitment is one of the factors of HRD/HRM policy for an effective organization/ group. Many major reviews of commitment theory and research are available (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1991; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001) Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997) compiled a list of definitions and analyzed the similarities and differences. The similarities served as the basis for a definition of what they considered the "core essence" of commitment. It is indeed that commitment is a force that binds an individual to a course of action that is of relevance to a particular target.

Various studies have been recorded on the phenomenon, which support job satisfaction and also support a positive relationship between organizational commitment and desirable outcomes such as performance, turnover and absenteeism (Mowday, Steers and Porter, 1979; Mathieu and Zajec, 1990). Moreover, an evidence have already been adduced, from the study of Luthans and Wahl (1992), they emphasized that employee/ individual commitment relates to other desirable outcomes such as, the perception of warm, supportive organizational climate. Ahmad and Ansari (1999) found that blue-collar workers are comparatively more prone to higher degree of organizational commitment than owners of the flour mills although, both the group had indicated favorable inclination to organizational commitment. In addition to this, an important study on "organizational commitment versus organizational change" have also been conducted by Ahmad (2000) and he pointed out that organizational commitment is not as the function of organizational change for both the group of blue-collar and white collar employees especially in saree manufacturing companies. Moreover, an attempt was made by Mishra & Srivastava (2001) to find out the moderating effect of the job stress on the organizational commitment and job satisfaction relationship and they found that job stress has moderating effect on organizational commitment and job satisfaction relationship.

Having reviewed the literature on the proposed research topic, it has been observed that the studies of organizational commitment being negligible number in Indian context especially in North Bihar context and this study of organizational commitment has still not been investigated with particular reference to private and

government school teachers covering Bihar state. Hence, the present study is of immense value and it will fill the void of knowledge in the area concerned although, both the group of private and government high school teachers are engaged in performing their job for the promotion of nation's building, process and communication. Hence, the main objective of the present study is to test the following hypotheses.

- There will be no significant difference between the private school and government school teachers group in terms of their extent of organizational commitment.
- Private high school teachers will have higher degree of organizational commitment than their colleagues who are working in Govt. High School.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample:

The sample of this study consisted of one hundred fifty teachers (N=120) comprising private high school teachers (n=60) and government high school teachers (n=60). They were selected randomly from different private high school and government high schools situated at in and around Darbhanga district. The age of the subjects ranged from 29-52.

Tools:

- (i) For measuring commitment, "Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ)" developed by Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979) was used. This schedule consisted of 15 items with seven alternative responses ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly Agree". In this questionnaire, six items were negatively phrased with reversely scored items whereas; the high score indicated the higher degree of organizational commitment. The reliability of the scale was tested with the split-half method and it was found to be .78 which was highly significant.
- (ii) Biographical Information Blank (BIB) was also prepared and used for analyzing the obtained results. Information included in it was like age, income, job tenure, number of depends, total working experience, qualifications, etc.

[Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers](#)

Procedure:

These two materials were in printed form and were administered on each woman schools teachers of primary and middle schools teachers by giving assurance that information provided by them will be kept strictly confidential.

The responses were scored according to the procedure and the individual scores were obtained. Having obtained the data, the data were tabulated for giving statistical treatment for obtaining the results and presented in tables. Finally, the results were discussed and the formulated hypothesis was tested.

RESULTS

In order to test the formulated hypothesis i.e. ; Government High School teachers and Private High School teachers will not differ in terms of their degree of organizational commitment, table-1 clearly indicated that the mean value of organizational commitment score of Government High School teachers group is very high in comparison to the Private High School teachers group, so, both the groups, Government school and Private School teachers significantly differ in terms of their degree of organizational commitment as 't' = 5.39 have been found highly significant at .01 level of confidence, Therefore, the proposed hypothesis stands rejected.

TABLE -1

Showing Significance of Difference in the Extent of Organizational Commitment as a Function of Group Difference

Group	N=120	Organizational commitment		't'	Level of significance
	n	Mean	S.D.		
Govt. High School Teachers	60	87.25	8.67	5.39	.01
Pvt. High School Teachers	60	80.29	4.87		

It is an important to point out that almost all the teachers either from the group of Government High School or Private High School especially from where the sample has been drawn have been found to have higher degree of perceived reactions to organizational commitment as it is evident from the mean value i.e. $x = 87.25$ and 80.29 with an SD for Government and Private High School teachers respectively (table-I), although, both the group of teachers have indicated favorable inclination to their extent of perceived commitment as the maximum score of organizational commitment is 105.

Table – 2 Showing the Comparative Difference between the Govt. High School and Pvt. High School Teachers Group on Their Extent of Organizational Commitment

Levels	Govt. High School Teachers		Pvt. High School Teachers	
	n=60	Percentage	n=60	Percentage
High	28	46.67%	23	38.33%
Moderate	20	33.33%	19	31.67%
Low	12	20.00%	18	30.00%

Table-2 also depicts the clear cut picture regarding the levels of perceived reactions of Government High School teachers and Private High School teachers group towards their perceived organizational commitment (OC). As it could be seen from the table-2, 46.67% teachers from Government High School group had shown higher degree of organizational commitment than Private High School teacher group i.e. 38.33%. It is also evident from the table, 33.33% teachers from Government High School teachers group have been found possessing moderate level of commitment than Private High School teachers group i.e. 31.67% which is comparatively lesser degree, whereas, 30.00% teachers from Private High School group had low degree of organizational commitment which is comparatively higher than Government school teachers group i.e. 20.00%.

Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers

Aforementioned results can also be concluded that most of the teachers from Government High School teachers group are more prone to have higher degree of organizational commitment than Private High School teachers group especially from where the sample has been drawn for the present piece of research work. Thus the formulated hypothesis i.e. ‘Private high school teachers will have higher degree of organizational commitment than their colleagues who are working in Govt. High School’ also stands rejected.

The above mentioned results concerning comparative difference on the levels of perceived reactions on the items of organizational commitment scale can also be observed by illustrating the following pie-chart.

Pie-Charts Showing the Comparative Difference between the Group of Government High School and Private High School Teachers on Their Extent of Organizational Commitment.

DISCUSSIONS

In the light of the results obtained, it is clear from the table-1 and 2 that all the teachers either Government High School or Private High School teachers group who are engaged to serve their services for the promotion of society in general and for the nation building in particular have shown favorable inclination on their perception of organizational commitment (OC). Although, the results also reveal the fact that the teachers from the Government High School teachers group were found comparatively more prone to higher degree of organizational commitment than Private High School teachers group, whereas , both the groups have been found, significantly unrelated to each other ($t = 5.39, P < .01$) as it is evident from table-1. In connection with such type of results, it is to point out that the results obtained seem to be quite logical that Government High School group of the teachers are basically technical and skillful according to the nature of job and they spend much time to fulfill their aim than private high school teachers. Hence, it seems that the private high school teachers group has shown low degree of organizational commitment. Thus, it is to be pointed out that the commitment depicts the firm and unchanging orientation in support of one's belief in his principles that's why Government High School teachers group experience significantly higher degree of commitment towards their profession, Moreover, teachers

[Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers](#)

group, working in private schools have to perform their job with the set directions and ideas under the pressure of management so they have been found little bit low commitment in comparison to Government High School teachers group, although, both the group of teachers have shown favorable inclination towards commitment.

Before terminating the discussion of results, it is necessary to throw light on some of the observations as experienced by the present investigator. It is because of the fact that the craze of the day especially in teaching profession, hence, symbolize a mark of social status in this modern materialistic world where the qualities of the persons are not important but the materials followed by quality they possess are the real indicators of one's position or status (Ahmad,2000). Thus, all the teachers either, from Government High School or Private High School feel pleasure in taking up challenges while choosing profession as teaching especially in Darbhanga from where the sample has been drawn have been found conducive.

CONCLUSION

In the light of the results obtained and its interpretations the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Significance of difference has been found between Government High School and Private High School teachers group in terms of their degree of organizational commitment.
2. Government High School teachers group have been found comparatively more prone to higher degree of organizational commitment than Private High School teachers group.
3. Both the group of teachers (Government High School and Private School) has indicated favorable inclination towards organizational commitment.
4. Observations have revealed such type of facts that all teachers either from Government and Private High School group, they need to serve their services for the promotion of society in general and for the nation's building in particular without having any feeling of shyness, inferiority and sense of losing esteem

needs. Thus, they have been found to have greater sense of commitment in their profession.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, Anis (2000). Organizational commitment versus organizational change: A comparative study. **Social Science International**, Vol. 16, No.1 & 2, pp. 20-23.
- Ahmad, Anis and Ansari, Faiz A (1999). Organizational commitment Amongst Flour Mills Workers: - A Comparative Study. **Social Science International**, Vol.15, No. 2, pp.31-38
- Gupta, M. and Gehlawat, M. (2013). A Study of the Correlates of Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers. **Issues and Ideas in Education**, Vol. 1 March 2013 pp. 59–71.
- Kumari, S., & Jafri, S. (2011). Levels of Organizational Commitment of Male and Female Teachers of Secondary Schools. **Journal of Community Guidance & Research**, 28(1), 37-47.
- Luthans Fred; La Vonne K. Wahl and Steinhaus, Carols. (1992). The importance of special support for Employee Commitment. **Organization Development Journal**, (winter), pp 1-10.
- Matheiu, J.E. & Zajac, D. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organizational commitment. **Psychological Bulletin**, 108, pp. 171-194
- Meyer J.P. & Allen. N.J. (1991). A three component conceptualization of organizational commitment. **Human Resource Management Review**, 1, pp. 61-68.
- Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (1997). Commitment in the workplace: theory, research and implications. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Meyer, J.P. & Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the work place: Towards a general model. **Human Resource Management Review**, 11, pp. 299-326.

Benkat Krishna Bharti / Extent of Perceived Organizational Commitment among Private and Government High School Teachers

- Mishra, P.C. and Srivastava, S. (2001). Job Stress as a Moderator Variable of the Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction Relationship. **Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology**, Vol. 27, No. 1-2, pp. 45-49.
- Misra, S., Ansari, N. and Khan, S.A. (2009). A comparative study of organizational commitment and organizational health among public and private school teachers. **Indian Journal of Psychology and Mental Health**, 3(5), 42-48.
- Mowday, R.T.; Porter, L.W. and Steers, R.M. (1982). Employee Organizational Linkages. Academic Press, New York.
- Mowday. R.T.; Steers, R.M and Porter. L.W. (1979). The Measurement of Organizational Commitment. **Journal of Vocational Behavior**, Vol.–14, pp. 46-52.
- Nagar, K. (2012). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction among teachers during times of burnout. Vikalpa: **The Journal for Decision Makers**, 37(2), 43-60.
- Suki, N., & Suki, N. (2011). Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment: The Effect of Gender. **International journal of psychology research**, 6(5), 1-15.
- Zilli, A. S., & Zahoor, Z. (2012). Organizational Commitment among Male and Female Higher Education Teachers. **Indian Journal of Psychology and Education**, 2(1), 55-60.